

OUTCOMES OF WORKING WITH PARENTS COUNSELING FOR EDUCATORS MODERN FORMS OF WORKING WITH PARENTS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Improving the system of pre-school education, bringing it up to the requirements of world educational standards is one of the priorities of public policy. The experience of developed countries shows that this factor plays a special role in the development of countries where children have reached adulthood. Only if we can bring up intelligent, high-spirited people, we will be able to achieve the goals we have set for ourselves, and prosperity and development will be established in our country. Improving the educational process on the basis of modern educational concepts shows that one of the most important tasks of our state is to bring up a harmoniously developed generation that will realize the national idea.

ABSTRACT

Today, an educator armed with all-round knowledge can express his rational solution in any situation. Friendly communication between parents and children is one of the most effective ways of cooperation.

Today, one of the urgent tasks is to bring up preschool children to be fully developed, physically healthy, mentally mature and spiritually formed. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" in the implementation of such tasks. September 23, 2020 No. ZRU-637 [2], June 18, 2018 "State requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [1], October 22, 2019 "Republic of Uzbekistan Law "On Preschool Education and Upbringing", "Concept of development of preschool education until 2030", May 8, 2019 PF-4312 "On approval of the Concept of development of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan" Decree PF-4312 [3] defines a number of tasks for the comprehensive development, education and preparation of children of primary and

preschool age for school education. Tasks aimed at improving the quality and efficiency of the preschool education system defined in [4].

In his address to the Parliament of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 24, 2020, the President of Uzbekistan said in his report "On priorities for 2020" [5]: They are three - science, enlightenment and the digital economy. It is planned to increase the coverage of preschool children to 60%. New schools will be built, including private ones, and existing ones will be renovated.

Recognizing that the above-mentioned issues are, in fact, the main principle of the State's requirements, "the uniqueness of the child", "the importance of protecting and ensuring the rights of the child", "the key role of adults in children's education and development" , requires direct, constant and effective cooperation of educators and parents. Indeed, the role of the family in the formation of personality is great. Mentally, morally pure, physically strong children grow up in exemplary families. That is why creating and strengthening a healthy family environment is a matter of national importance.

Parents play a special role in the upbringing of their children, in their lifestyle, in their behavior, in their communication skills, and in their development into perfect human beings. It is in our independent country that this issue is legally guaranteed. First of all, parents have equal rights and responsibilities towards their children. Caring for a child is not only a moral right but also a constitutional right and duty of a parent.

According to the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, living with their children, dealing with their upbringing, independent exercise of parental rights, care for the child's health, physical, mental, spiritual and moral development to ensure that children receive the necessary level of education as defined by law, to protect the rights and interests of children.

No matter how hard preschool educators work with parents today, the quality and effectiveness of education depends in many ways on the environment in which the child grows up. Nowadays, the regular employment of parents and modern techniques are weakening their focus on raising children. Parents are reluctant to talk to their children about their interest in listening to their dreams. The basis of the interaction of family and preschool education organizations is that they are responsible for the upbringing of children, and all other social institutions call for support and supplementation of their educational activities. This is part of the policy of family upbringing in the country in the past.

The thinker Abu Rayhan Beruni can be seen in his writings paying close attention to family upbringing. Beruni advises to be sincere and honest in family relations. He believes that family happiness can be achieved not only with external beauties, but also with internal beauties. Education is provided first in the family and then in educational institutions along with education. The most important task of an individual's decision-making is to inculcate in the student the beliefs and ideals that meet the requirements of morality. The following special forms of work are used to work with parents: conversations, consultations, visits to families, inviting

some parents to kindergarten, the use of special souvenirs and portable folders. The purpose of visiting the child's home is to get acquainted with the family situation, the child's family behavior, interests, parents and family members, as well as to acquaint parents with effective methods of child rearing and to learn and popularize the family's positive parenting experiences. The educator should go to the child's home not as an inspector, but as a friend, as an assistant in a difficult task such as raising a child, and to treat family members with courtesy and politeness. Before going to each family, the educator should set a clear goal and determine in advance what the topic will be discussed. In order to gain the respect and trust of parents, the educator first gives parents feedback on the child's positive qualities and how to organize the child's home life, what can be read and told to him, the child's agenda, provides advice on the content and methods of educational work, such as participation in family work, upbringing in the spirit of respect for adults. Of course, the educator's work with the family takes into account the child's age, abilities, and characteristics. Parents or other family members are invited to the preschool to ensure that the educator's advice and counsel to the parents is credible. In this way, parents can see how the child is on duty or how he or she is playing before the trip, making sure that the child is learning and able.

The purpose and content of the visit to the family should be reflected in the plan and report of the educator, in the diary. The caregiver should visit each child's family at least 2 times a year. The content of the work with parents is varied, requiring some issues to be discussed together.

For example:

- The role of the family in the upbringing of children, the laws on the role of parents, the preparation of children for school;
- about the annual work plan of the preschool institution;
- Issues related to the work of the parent community.

Forms of group work include parent group and general meetings, consultations, conferences, and parent nights to discuss these issues as a group.

It is important to establish a library and a parent corner in preschool to help parents. Popular scientific literature recommended to parents selected by the director of the institution, stylists and educators will help parents to acquire certain knowledge about the correct and rational organization of children's upbringing in the family, physical, physiological, mental and intellectual development of children.

In the family, the father and mother are equally responsible for the upbringing of the child. The child looks at the adults in the family and draws his own conclusions

Of course, it takes time for conversations to be open and credible. A skilled MTT educator follows the following principles when communicating with families:

- ☑ Finds time, creates opportunities;
- ☑ Encourages parents to share their thoughts, joys, worries and intentions;
- ☑ Chooses a place where you can have a face-to-face conversation;
- ☑ Information is always treated as confidential;

Scientific research and experiments show that strong collaboration between educators, families and community

members can make a positive contribution to children's development and education.

"In order to ensure the full development of the child, the preschool organization can use the following forms of interaction with parents:

- Preschool education should take into account the expectations of parents;
- Inform parents about early development;
- Involve parents in active participation in the educational process;
- Support the initiative of parents to participate in the activities of preschool educational institutions.

Families share the most personal information with caregivers, so it's important to keep it confidential. Working parents often have very little free time. That's why natural informal situations where educators can talk to families are crucial to developing the relationship between kindergarten and home. When informal time is set for communication, depending on the parents' possibilities, the meeting schedule should be varied and adapted to the conditions of free conversation at the beginning and end of the day.

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